

NOTES

and the overall reaction for the formation of the 1 : 1 : 1 ternary chelate as :

where M^{2+} stands for metal ion, H_2A for HQSA and H_2L^+ for His.HCl. If K' and K'' are the equilibrium constants of reactions (i) and (ii) respectively, then

$$K' = \frac{[MAL^-][H^+]^2}{[MA][H_2L^+]} \quad \dots (1)$$

and

$$K'' = \frac{[MAL^-][H^+]^4}{[M^{2+}][H_2A][H_2L^+]} \quad \dots (2)$$

If T_M , T_A and T_L represent the total concentrations of the metal, the primary and secondary ligand species respectively and T_{OH} is the concentration of the base added to the reaction mixture during the titration and neglecting the concentrations of OH^- , A^{2-} and L^- in the pH-range studied, it follows that :

$$T_M = [M^{2+}] + [MA] + [MAL^-] \quad \dots (3)$$

$$T_A = [H_2A] + [HA^-] + [MA] + [MAL^-] \quad \dots (4)$$

$$T_L = [H_2L^+] + [HL] + [MAL^-] \quad \dots (5)$$

$$T_{OH} + [H^+] = 2[MA] + 4[MAL^-] + [HA^-] + [HL] \quad \dots (6)$$

In a 1 : 1 : 1 reaction mixture, using the equations (3)-(6) and relations for the dissociation constants of ligands and equilibrium constant (K_1) of the reaction, $M^{2+} + H_2A \rightleftharpoons MA + 2H^+$ it may be shown that :

$$a[M^{2+}]^2 + b[M^{2+}] - c = 0 \quad \dots (7)$$

where $a = K_1(1+y)/[H^+]^2$, $b = x+y+2xy$, $c = \{(4-m)T_M - [H^+]\}xy$, $x = 1+k_1/[H^+]$ and $y = 1+k'_1/[H^+]$

k_1 and k'_1 are the first dissociation constants of HQSA and His. HCl respectively. The values of K_1 ($\log K_{MA} = 11.92$ and 9.02 for Cu^{2+} -HQSA and Ni^{2+} -HQSA systems respectively) were taken from the literature⁸.

The equilibrium concentration of the free metal ions present in the reaction mixture was determined by solving equation (7). The concentrations of other species involved in the equilibrium relations were then calculated from the above equations together with the values of equilibrium constants K' and K'' . Further, the formation constant of the ternary complex (K_{MAL}) which may be defined as :

$$K_{MAL} = \frac{[MAL^-]}{[MA][L^-]} = \frac{K'}{k'_1 k'_2} \quad \dots (8)$$

and the overall stability constant of the mixed ligand chelate :

$$\beta_{MAL} = \frac{[MAL^-]}{[M^{2+}][A^{2-}][L^-]} = \frac{K''}{k_1 k_2 k'_1 k'_2} \quad \dots (9)$$

The values of the equilibrium and chelate formation constants of the ternary complexes are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM AND CHELATE FORMATION CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND CHELATES ($t = 30 \pm 1^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1$ KNO ₃)				
System	$-\log K'$	$-\log K''$	$\log K_{MAL}$	$\log \beta_{MAL}$
Cu(II)-HQSA-His	5.55 ± 0.12	6.18 ± 0.12	9.67 ± 0.12	21.59 ± 0.12
Ni(II)-HQSA-His	7.37 ± 0.13	10.90 ± 0.16	7.85 ± 0.16	16.87 ± 0.16

Other evidence supporting the formation of ternary complexes is also given by the colour change from the yellowish green of the 1 : 1 M^{2+} -HQSA binary complex and blue of the 1 : 1 M^{2+} -His binary complex to dark green in the presence of both the ligands. No precipitation at any stage in case of ternary systems also support the formation of ternary complexes.

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A Rapid Method for Selective Separation and Estimation of Chromium in Some Ores and Alloys by Hydrated Zirconium Dioxide Ion-Exchanger

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TANDON *et al.*¹ reported the high K_a -value ($> 10^4$) of chromium(VI) on hydrated zirconium dioxide which inspired us to study for selective separation of Cr(VI) from some ores and alloys using hydrated zirconium dioxide ion-exchanger.

In our previous work² with organic cation exchange resin Dowex-50W-X8, it was observed that Cr(VI) was reduced to Cr(III) by organic exchanger. Similar behaviour of Cr(VI) was indicated by earlier worker³⁻⁵.

This paper reports systematic studies, rapid and selective recovery of Cr(VI) from some ores and alloys. No reduction of Cr(VI) takes place due to contact with hydrated zirconium dioxide ion-exchanger.

Experimental

Apparatus : A glass column (i.d. 1.2 cm) was used for column operation. 3.0 gms of hydrated zirconium dioxide (OH⁻-form) was taken in the column and flow rate was initially maintained at 1.5 ml/minute.

For pH measurement an ELICO pH meter model No. LI-10 was used. Analytical balance Awa. Labor type 707.04 (Germany) was used.

Reagents and Chemicals :

Zirconyl oxy-chloride was of reagent grade quality (Indian Rare Earth Co. Ltd.). All other reagents, were of AnalaR grade (BDH/E. Merck/Pfizer).

Extra low carbon alloy (Lot No. 1627 A) and DSP alloy steel (A) supplied by Durgapur Alloy Steel Plant, and B.A.S. Stainless Steel (69a) and chrome-iron ore (49f) were used.

Synthesis of Hydrated Zirconium Dioxide :

Hydrated zirconium dioxide was prepared by adding 0.1(M) aqueous ammonia to 0.1M zirconium oxychloride solution in 0.1(M) HCl (1 : 1 V/V) as described by Tandon *et al*². The air dried product was grinded to 100-200 mesh size and ignited at 300° for an hour before use.

Distribution Co-efficients (K_a) of Cr(VI), Fe(III) and Ni(II) :

The chief constituents of the samples under investigation are nickel, iron and chromium. So the distribution co-efficients (K_a) of Ni(II), Fe(III) and Cr(VI) were determined as usual⁶ at pH 1.5-2.0, adjusted with dilute HCl on hydrated zirconium dioxide exchanger by shaking 12 hours intermittently. The concentration of Ni(II), Fe(III) and Cr(VI) solutions were kept around 5×10^{-4} (M). Fe(III) and Ni(II) in solutions were estimated by EDTA (disodium salt) titration⁷ and Cr(VI) was estimated spectrophotometrically⁷. The K_a values were then calculated as before⁶. The K_a value of Ni(II), Fe(III) and Cr(VI) are 2.56, 0.71 and 1332 respectively.

Since hydrated zirconium dioxide acts as an anion exchanger at low pH, those K_a values are in quite agreement with what is expected. It is interesting to note that no reduction of Cr(VI) takes place in contact with the exchanger bed for a long period of time.

Elution : From preliminary elution studies of Cr(VI), Fe(III) and Ni(II), it is observed that Cr(VI) remains strongly adsorbed on hydrated zirconium dioxide (OH⁻-form) bed in dil HCl solution (pH 1.5) where as Fe(III) and Ni(II) percolate through the exchanger bed. On washing the exchanger column with 0.1M HCl (pH 1) Fe(III) and Ni(II) free from Cr(VI) are quantitatively collected in the effluent. The flow rate is kept at 1.5 ml/minute. After removal Fe(III) and Ni(II), Cr(VI) can be eluted quantitatively with 2.0M KOH solution.

Procedure : The ion-exchanger column (OH⁻-form) was treated with 40 ml of water at pH 1.5 (adjusted with dil HCl) before passing the test solution. A known volume of test solution was taken accurately and was passed through the exchanger bed at the flow rate of 1.5 ml/minute. The column was then washed with 60 ml of 0.1(M) HCl (pH 1). Fe(III) and Ni(II) were percolated out with the effluent and washing liquid. The adsorbed Cr(VI) was then eluted quantitatively with 60 ml of 2(M) KOH solution.

Results and Discussion

A synthetic mixture of ferro-chrome alloy, extra low carbon ferro-chrome alloy [Lot No. 1627 A], DSP alloy steel (A), B.A.S. stainless (69a) and B.A.S. chrome-iron ore (49f) were studied for selective separation and estimation of Cr(VI) by column chromatography. In the synthetic mixture, the amount of Fe(III) and Cr(VI) were varied from 1 : 10 to 10 : 1 in the ratio by weight. With the increase or decrease of the amount of Fe(III) in the mixture, the volume of washing solution is increased or decreased slightly. Similar results were observed in the eluant volume of Cr(VI) also. Fe(III) and Cr(VI) were estimated volumetrically⁷. Ni(II) was estimated with EDTA (disodium salt)⁶. In our previous work⁸ it was observed that Fe(III) was adsorbed partly by hydrated stannic oxide exchanger during chrome-iron alloy analysis. But in this method no such adsorption of Fe(III) is occurred. So it is a better method for the analysis of chrome-iron ores and alloys than the previous one. This method is applicable also when Cr(VI) is present in the sample in microgram quantity. In that case Cr(VI) was estimated spectrophotometrically⁹. Hence, this method can be used to remove toxic Cr(VI) from polluted water. The results in Table I indicate that accuracy and precision of the recommended procedure is satisfactory. The method is simple, rapid and it takes only 2 hours time for complete analysis of chrome-iron ore.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF FERRO-CHROME ORES AND ALLOYS

Sl. No.	Sample with composition	Metal analysed	Amount taken (mg)	Amount recovered (mg)	% of Standard recovery	Deviation very
1.	Synthetic mixture Fe(III):Cr(VI)~1:10 Cr	Fe	4.74	4.72	99.56	0.04
		Cr	43.38	43.61	100.60	0.3
2.	Synthetic mixture Fe(III):Cr(VI)~10:1 Cr	Fe	47.26	46.96	99.40	0.25
		Cr	5.06	5.09	100.60	0.03
3.	Synthetic ferro-chrome alloy Fe(III)-6%, Cr(VI)-72%	Fe	6.33	6.34	100.15	0.02
		Cr	12.70	12.78	100.70	0.05
4.	Extra low-carbon ferro-chrome alloy (Lot No. 1627 A) Fe-26.88%,Cr-72.53%	Fe	5.24	5.29	100.98	0.04
		Cr	12.33	12.16	98.60	0.20
5.	Stainless steel (69a) Cr-18.4% Ni-8.2%	Fe	35.60	34.73	97.60	0.80
		Cr	9.34	9.45	101.2	0.13
		Ni	3.67	3.69	100.60	0.01
6.	DSP alloy steel (A) Cr-23.75% Ni-20.41%	Fe	20.32	20.32	100.00	0.01
		Cr	9.52	9.41	98.86	0.12
		Ni	8.25	8.12	98.42	0.15
7.	Chrome-iron ore(49f) Cr ₂ O ₃ -43.1% FeO 15.3%	Fe	1.60	1.59	99.40	0.01
		Cr	3.94	3.95	100.20	0.01
8.*	Chrome-iron ore (49f)	Cr	10 μg	9.9 μg	99.00	0.08

* Exchanger taken -1.5g, column length (1.2 × 1.3) cm, Eluant volume -15 ml.

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Thermolysis of Substituted Ortho-Hydroxy Acetophenone Oxime Complexes with Bivalent Metals-Part II

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ROLE of ortho-hydroxy keto oximes in the last one decade has encouraged the chemists due to their inevitable application¹⁻⁵ in various fields. The ineffable efficiency of these compounds is due to the presence of phenolic group in vicinity of keto oxime group to act as bidentate ligands with bivalent metal ions for the formation of six membered ring of stable chelates. This manuscript records the vivid TGA interpretation of palladium, nickel and copper complexes with 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro acetophenone oxime, 2-hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone oxime and 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone oxime.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligands :

The 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro acetophenone oxime (HMCAOX) ; m.p. 146°, 2-hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone oxime (HCAOX) ; m.p. 181° and 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone oxime (HBAOX) ; m.p. 169-170° were prepared as early reported⁶.

The metal solutions were prepared by dissolving AnalaR grade metal chloride or sulphates in double-distilled water. The solutions of ligands were made in ethanol.

A Stanton thermobalance, model HT-SM range ambient 1600° with an accuracy of 1 mg was used for recording TGA at a heating rate of 5° per minute.

Preparation of complexes :

The complexes of palladium, nickel and copper were prepared by usual gravimetric method⁷ at pH 0.6 to 0.9, 5.5 to 8 and 3.0 to 4.5 respectively employing the solution of aforesaid oximes. These complexes are non-electrolytic in nature and are soluble in common non-polar solvents.

Results and Discussion

Thermolysis of Pd(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes with HBAOX : It is obvious from

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